

New trends in population dynamics

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Abstract

We present in this paper a deterministic model for a general human population dynamics. The main variables are population and welfare. These variables are considered to calculate UN's indices like HDI¹, HPI-2², GDI³ and GEM⁴. The model has been validated for the case of Spain in the period 1999-2005.

¹ Human Development Index, calculated by the UN.

² Human Poverty Index for selected OECD countries, calculated by the UN

³ Gender-Related Development Index, calculated by the UN.

⁴ Gender Empowerment measure, calculated by the UN.

Key words: Human Poverty Index for selected OECD countries (HPI-2), Gender-Related Development Index (GDI), Gender Empowerment measure (GEM), Human Development Index (HDI), dynamic model, population density, welfare variables, fertility rates, death rates, immigration rates, emigration rates.

Resumen

En éste artículo presentamos un modelo determinista para la dinámica de población humana. Las principales variables son la población y las variables calidad de vida. Estas variables son consideradas para calcular índices usados por la ONU como son IDH¹, IPH-2², IDG³ e IPG⁴. El modelo ha sido validado para el caso de España durante el periodo 1999-2005.

¹ Índice de Desarrollo Humano, calculado por la ONU.

² Índice de Pobreza Humana para países de la OCDE, calculado por la ONU.

³ Índice de Desarrollo por Géneros, calculado por la ONU.

⁴ Índice de Pobreza por Géneros, calculado por la ONU.

Palabras clave: Índice de Pobreza Humana para países de la OCDE (HPI-2), Índice de Desarrollo por Géneros (GDI), Índice de Pobreza por Géneros (GEM), Índice de Desarrollo Humano (HDI), modelo dinámico, densidad de población, variables de bienestar, tasas de fertilidad, tasas de mortalidad, tasas de inmigración, tasas de emigración.

1. Introduction

After working with other population dynamics models, our interest is focused now on the introduction of welfare variables. In a recent

work (Caselles, A., Micó, J.C., Soler, D., Sanz, M.T. (2008)) we presented a first approximation to this new model in which we did not distinguish between sexes or ages; we considered only total populations. Trying to

carry out a more detailed work we have checked in the UN's publications (<http://www.madrid.org/iestadis/fijas/otros/indecoaIDHonu.htm>) about the Human Development Index (HDI).

The HDI is a summary measure of human development. It measures the average achievements in a country in three basic dimensions of human development:

- A long and healthy life, given by life expectancy.
- Knowledge, given by the adult literacy rate (with two-thirds weight) and the combined primary, secondary and tertiary gross enrolment ratio (with one-third weight).
- A decent standard of living, given by GDP¹ per capita in purchasing power parity (PPP) terms in US dollars.

Although the concept of human development is wider enough to be measured by only one index, the HDI is the alternative to the use of the Interior Gross Product (IGP), as a measure of the human well-being and it is useful to approach the information located in the tables of UN's indicators, which we can find in (<http://www.madrid.org/iestadis/fijas/otros/indecoaIDHonu.htm>).

Now, in this work we introduce three news indices: Human Poverty Index for selected OECD countries (HPI-2), Gender-Related Development Index (GDI) and Gender Empowerment measure (GEM).

While the HDI measures average achievement, the *HPI-2* measures deprivations in the four basic dimensions of human development captured in the HDI:

- A long and healthy life-vulnerability to death at a relatively early age, given by the probability at birth of not surviving to age 60.
- Knowledge-exclusion from the world of reading and communications, given by the percentage of adults (ages 16-65) lacking functional literacy skills.
- A decent standard of living, given by the percentage of people living below the income poverty line (50% of the median adjusted household disposable income).

- Social exclusion, given by the rate of long-term unemployment (12 months or more).

The GDI adjusts the average achievement to reflect the inequalities between men and women in the following dimensions:

- A long and healthy life, given by life expectancy at birth.
- Knowledge, given by the adults' literacy rate (with two-thirds weight) and the combined primary, secondary and tertiary gross enrolment ratio (with one-third weight).
- A decent standard of living, given by estimated earned income (PPP US\$).

Focusing on women's opportunities rather than their capabilities, the GEM captures gender inequality in three key areas:

- Political participation and decision-making power, given by women's and men's percentage shares of parliamentary seats.
- Economic participation and decision-making power, given by two indicators: women's and men's percentage shares of positions as legislators, senior officials and managers and, women's and men's percentage shares of professional and technical positions.
- Power over economic resources given by women's and men's estimated earned income (PPP US\$).

The definition of these four indices allows us to create a deterministic model through the following steps:

- Find the relevant factors or variables.
- Find the influence relationships between the factors or variables previously identified.
- Find the equations or functional relationships that allow determining the behavior of each variable.
- Search for the necessary historical data for the calculation of the numeric constants that appear in the global model of the behavior of the system.
- Validate the model.

¹ Gross Domestic Product

Indicator	Maximum Value	Minimum Value
Life expectancy at birth (years)	85	25
Adult literacy rate (%)	100	0
Combined gross enrolment ratio (%)	100	0
GDP per capita (PPP US\$)	40000	100

Table 1: Goalposts for calculating the HDI

2. Calculating the different indices and variables' identification

In this section we explain the different variables that are necessary to calculate the referred indices. With this aim, we have followed the Brainstorming method (Micó, Caselles, and Soler, 2006) to identify the elements. The used codification consists of giving a short name to each element taken into account.

Our objective in this section is to try to obtain the kind of dependence of the female birth, male birth, female death, and male death rates on the HDI, GDI, GEM and HPI-2.

The immigration rate and emigration rate (for females and males) are considered as depending only on time.

2.1. HDI

Before calculating the HDI, an index needs to be created for each one of its dimensions. To calculate these indices - the life expectancy, education and GDP indices - the minimum and maximum values (goalposts) are chosen for each underlying indicator.

Performance in each dimension is expressed as a value between 0 and 1 by applying the following general formula:

$$\text{Dimension Index} = \frac{\text{actual value} - \text{minimum value}}{\text{maximum value} - \text{minimum value}}$$

The different equations to compute the HDI are:

The Life Expectancy Index²

The life expectancy index measures the relative achievement of a country in life expectancy at birth.

$$\text{LEI} := \frac{\text{LE} - \text{min le}}{\text{max le} - \text{min le}} \quad (1)$$

The education index

The education index measures a country's relative achievement in both adult literacy and combined primary, secondary and tertiary gross enrolment.

First, an index for adult literacy and another one for combined gross enrolment are calculated.

Literacy Rate Adults³

$$\text{LRA} := \frac{\text{LA} - \text{min la}}{\text{max la} - \text{min la}} \quad (2)$$

Gross Rate Registered to level primary, secondary and tertiary⁴

$$\text{GRR} := \frac{\text{GR} - \text{min gr}}{\text{max gr} - \text{min gr}} \quad (3)$$

Then these two indices are combined to create the education index, with two-thirds weight given to adult literacy and one-third weight to combined gross enrolment.

$$\text{IED} := \frac{2}{3}\text{LRA} + \frac{1}{3}\text{GRR} \quad (4)$$

The Interior Gross Product Index⁵

The GPI index is calculated using the adjusted GDP per capita (PPP US\$). It serves as a surrogate for all the dimensions of human development not reflected in *a long and healthy life* and in *knowledge*. Income is adjusted because achieving a respectable level of human development does not require unlimited income.

² Life expectancy at birth (LE)

³ Adults literacy rate (LA)

⁴ The combined primary, secondary and tertiary gross enrolment ratio (GR)

⁵ GDP per capita in purchasing power parity (PPP) terms in US dollars (GPI)

$$IGPI := \frac{\text{Log(GPI)} - \text{Log(min igp)}}{\text{Log(max igp)} - \text{Log(min igp)}} \quad (5)$$

The Human Development Index

Once the dimension indices have been calculated, determining the HDI is straightforward. It is a simple average of the three dimension indices.

$$HDI := \frac{1}{3}LEI + \frac{1}{3}IGPI + \frac{1}{3}IED \quad (6)$$

2.2 HPI-2

Calculating the HPI-2 is more straightforward than calculating the HDI. The indicators used to measure the deprivations are already normalized between 0 and 100 (because they are expressed as percentages), so there is no need to create dimension indices for the HPI-2.

Given the following parameters:

- P_1 = Probability at birth of not surviving to age 60 (times 100),
- P_2 = Percentage of adults lacking functional literacy skills,
- P_3 = Percentage of population below income poverty line (50% of median adjusted household disposable income) and,
- P_4 = Rate of long-term unemployment (lasting 12 months or more),

the HPI-2 for selected OECD countries is given by:

$$HPI - 2 := \left[\frac{1}{4}(P_1^3 + P_2^3 + P_3^3 + P_4^3) \right]^{1/3} \quad (7)$$

2.3 GDI

The calculation of GDI involves three steps.

First, female and male indices in each dimension are calculated according to this general formula:

$$\text{Dimension Index} = \frac{\text{actual value} - \text{minimum value}}{\text{maximum value} - \text{minimum value}}$$

Second, the female and male indices in each dimension are combined in a way that penalizes the differences in achievement between men and women. The resulting index is calculated according to this general formula:

$$\text{Equally distributed index} = \left\{ \left[\text{female population share (female index}^{1-\varepsilon}) \right] + \left[\text{male population share (male index}^{1-\varepsilon}) \right] \right\}^{1/1-\varepsilon}$$

ε measures the aversion to inequality. In the GDI, $\varepsilon=2$.

Third, the GDI is calculated by combining the three equally distributed indices by a non-weighted average.

Indicator	Maximum Value	Minimum Value
Female life expectancy at birth (years).	87.5	27.5
Male life expectancy at birth (years).	82.5	22.5
Adult literacy rate (%).	100	0
Combined gross enrolment ratio (%).	100	0
Estimated earned income (PPP US\$).	40000	100

Table 2: Goalposts for calculating the GDI

Next, the different equations to compute the GDI are presented.

The equally distributed life Expectancy Index⁶

The first needed step is to calculate separate indices for female and male achievements in life expectancy using the general formula for dimension indices.

$$LEIF := \frac{LEF - \text{min lef}}{\text{max lef} - \text{min lef}} \quad (8)$$

$$LEIM := \frac{LEM - \text{min lem}}{\text{max lem} - \text{min lem}} \quad (9)$$

Next, the female and male indices are combined to create the equally distributed life expectancy

⁶ Female Life expectancy at birth (LEF), Male Life expectancy at birth (LEM)

index, using the general formula for equally distributed indices.

$$\text{LEID} := \frac{\text{Female Population Share}}{\text{LEIF}} - \frac{\text{Male Population Share}}{\text{LEIM}} \quad (10)$$

The equally distributed education index

Firstly, indices for the adult literacy rate and the combined primary, secondary and tertiary gross enrolment ratio are calculated separately for females and males. Calculating these indices is straightforward, since the indicators used are already normalized between 0 and 100.

Literacy Rate Adults⁷

$$\text{LRAF} := \frac{\text{LAF} - \text{min laf}}{\text{max laf} - \text{min laf}} \quad (11)$$

$$\text{LRAM} := \frac{\text{LAM} - \text{min lam}}{\text{max lam} - \text{min lam}} \quad (12)$$

Gross Rate Registered to levels primary, secondary and tertiary⁸

$$\text{GRRF} := \frac{\text{GRF} - \text{min grf}}{\text{max grf} - \text{min grf}} \quad (13)$$

$$\text{GRRM} := \frac{\text{GRM} - \text{min grm}}{\text{max grm} - \text{min grm}} \quad (14)$$

Secondly, the education index, which gives two-thirds weight to the adult literacy index and one-third weight to the gross enrolment index, is computed separately for females and males.

$$\text{IEDF} := \frac{2}{3}\text{LRAF} + \frac{1}{3}\text{GRRF} \quad (15)$$

$$\text{IEDM} := \frac{2}{3}\text{LRAM} + \frac{1}{3}\text{GRRM} \quad (16)$$

Finally, the female and male education indices are combined to create the equally distributed education index.

$$\text{IEDD} := \frac{\text{Female Population Share}}{\text{IEDF}} - \frac{\text{Male Population Share}}{\text{IEDM}} \quad (17)$$

The Equally distributed Interior Gross Product Index⁹

Firstly, female and male earned income (PPP US\$) are estimated. Then the income index is calculated for each gender. As with HDI, income is adjusted taking the logarithm of the estimated earned income (PPP US\$).

$$\text{IGPF} := \frac{\text{Log(GPF)} - \text{Log(min gpf)}}{\text{Log(max gpf)} - \text{Log(min gpf)}} \quad (18)$$

$$\text{IGPM} := \frac{\text{Log(GPM)} - \text{Log(min gpm)}}{\text{Log(max gpm)} - \text{Log(min gpm)}} \quad (19)$$

Finally, the female and male income indices are combined to create the equally distributed income index.

$$\text{IGPD} := \frac{\text{Female Population Share}}{\text{IGPF}} - \frac{\text{Male Population Share}}{\text{IGPM}} \quad (20)$$

The Gender-Related Development Index

Calculating GDI is straightforward. It's simply the non-weighted average of the three component indices: the equally distributed life expectancy index, the equally distributed education index and the equally distributed income index.

$$\text{GDI} := \frac{1}{3}\text{LEID} + \frac{1}{3}\text{IGPD} + \frac{1}{3}\text{IEDD} \quad (21)$$

2.4 GEM

For each of its three dimensions, an equally distributed equivalent percentage (EDEP) is calculated, as a population-weighted average, according to the following general formula:

⁷ Female Adults literacy rate (LAF), Male Adults literacy rate (LAM)

⁸ The female combined primary, secondary and tertiary gross enrolment ratio (GRF), The male combined primary, secondary and tertiary gross enrolment ratio (GRM)

⁹ Female GDP per capita in purchasing power parity (PPP) terms in US dollars (GPF), Male GDP per capita in purchasing power parity (PPP) terms in US dollars (GPM)

$$EDEP := (female\ index^{1-\varepsilon} + male\ index^{1-\varepsilon})^{1/(1-\varepsilon)}$$

Where: ε measures the aversion to inequality. *female index*^{1- ε} is named as *female population share* and *male index*^{1- ε} is named as *male population share*. In the GEM, $\varepsilon=2$.

For political and economical participation and decision-making, the EDEP is then indexed by dividing it by 50. The rationale for this indexation is that in an ideal society, with equal empowerment of the sexes, the GEM variables would equal 50%, that is, women's share would equal men's share for each variable.

Where a male or female index value is zero, the EDEP according to the above formula is not defined. However, the limit of EDEP, when the index tends towards zero, is zero. Accordingly, in these cases the value of the EDEP is set to zero.

Finally, GEM is calculated as a simple average of the three indexed EDEP.

We are going to explain now the different equations to compute GEM:

The EDEP for parliamentary representation

It measures the relative empowerment of women in terms of their political participation. The EDEP is calculated using female and male shares of the population and female and male percentage shares or parliamentary seats according to the general formula.

$$EDE1 := \frac{\frac{Female\ Population\ Share}{Female\ Parliamentary\ Share} - \frac{Male\ Population\ Share}{Male\ Parliamentary\ Share}}{50} \tag{22}$$

The EDEP for economic participation

Using the general formula, an EDEP is calculated for women's and men's percentage shares of positions as legislators, senior officials and managers, and another for women's and men's percentage shares of

professional and technical positions. The simple average of the two measures gives the EDEP for economic participation.

$$EDEP1\ for\ positions\ as\ legisl,\ senior\ offic\ and\ manag := \frac{\frac{Female\ Population\ Share}{Female\ Positions\ Share} - \frac{Male\ Population\ Share}{Male\ Positions\ Share}}{50} \tag{23}$$

$$EDEP2\ for\ professional\ and\ technical\ positions := \frac{\frac{Female\ Population\ Share}{Female\ Positions\ Share} - \frac{Male\ Population\ Share}{Male\ Positions\ Share}}{50} \tag{24}$$

$$EDE2 := \frac{EDEP1 - EDEP2}{2} \tag{25}$$

The EDEP for income

Earned income (PPP US\$) is estimated for women and men separately and then indexed to the scaled goalposts as was done for the GDI. For GEM, however, the income index is based on unadjusted values, not on the logarithm of the estimated earned income.

$$EGPF := \frac{GPF - min\ gpf}{max\ gpf - min\ gpf} \tag{26}$$

$$EGPM := \frac{GPM - min\ gpm}{max\ gpm - min\ gpm} \tag{27}$$

$$EDE3 := \frac{\frac{Female\ Population\ Share}{EGPF} - \frac{Male\ Population\ Share}{EGPM}}{2} \tag{28}$$

The Gender Empowerment measure

Once EDEP has been calculated for the three dimensions of GEM, determining GEM is straightforward. It is a simple average of the three EDEP indices:

$$GEM := \frac{1}{3}EDE1 + \frac{1}{3}EDE2 + \frac{1}{3}EDE3 \tag{29}$$

3. Model structure

In order to show how some variables influence others, we present the Forrester's diagram (Figure 1, Appendix I) corresponding to our model.

4. Fitting Variables

We have obtained the historical data of population from the database of the Spanish National Institute of Statistics (<http://www.ine.es>) for the period 1999-2005.

The fitted functions (immigration rate and emigration rate) have been obtained by using the packet *Nonlinear Regression* of MATHEMATICA 6.0 and we have used *Regint* (Caselles, 2008) for fitting the women's and men's death rate and the women's and men's birth rate to historical data.

We are going to comment next how the input variables have been adjusted from this information and how the possible faults of information have been resolved.

The justification of the choice of these adjustments is given through the figures that we show in APPENDIX I.

Firstly, for the immigration and emigration rates, the information corresponding to the period of application must be computed in a different way than the other rates. For immigration we have all the necessary information, but not for sexes, so we have decided to multiply by the proportion of each sex corresponding to the total population for each year. For emigration, the distinction by sexes has been performed in the same way. Nevertheless, the complete information exists only from the year 2002. In order to complete the information from 1996 to 2001, the information corresponding to these years in the city of Valencia (that appears in its web: <http://www.ayto-valencia.es>) has been multiplied by the proportion between the number of inhabitants in the city of Valencia and the number inhabitants in Spain. The considered functions, both for immigrations and for emigrations, are derived from logistics with positive parameters, as it has been done in (Micó, Caselles and Soler, 2006):

$$TFEM(t) = \frac{\beta_1 \cdot \exp(-\alpha_1 \cdot (t - \mu_1))}{(1 + \gamma_1 \cdot \exp(-\alpha_1 \cdot (t - \mu_1)))^2} + \frac{\beta_2 \cdot \exp(-\alpha_2 \cdot (t - \mu_2))}{(1 + \gamma_2 \cdot \exp(-\alpha_2 \cdot (t - \mu_2)))^2} \quad (30)$$

$$TMEM(t) = \frac{\beta_3 \cdot \exp(-\alpha_3 \cdot (t - \mu_3))}{(1 + \gamma_3 \cdot \exp(-\alpha_3 \cdot (t - \mu_3)))^2} + \frac{\beta_4 \cdot \exp(-\alpha_4 \cdot (t - \mu_4))}{(1 + \gamma_4 \cdot \exp(-\alpha_4 \cdot (t - \mu_4)))^2} \quad (31)$$

$$TFIN(t) = \frac{\beta_5}{(1 + \gamma_5 \cdot \exp(-\alpha_5 \cdot (t - \mu_5)))^2} \quad (32)$$

$$TMIN(t) = \frac{\beta_6}{(1 + \gamma_6 \cdot \exp(-\alpha_6 \cdot (t - \mu_6)))^2} \quad (33)$$

The mathematical structures of the fitted functions corresponding to emigration rate and immigration rate are also the indicated by Marchetti, Meyer and Ausubel (1996) for time rates, i.e., logistic functions (or sums of them).

Through figures 2, 3, 4 and 5 (APPENDIX I) we can observe that the functions are a very good approximation to the historical information.

Finally, for the adjustment of the birth rate and the death rate, we present an innovation with respect to other population-dynamics' models (Chowdhury and Allen, 2001), (Marchetti, Meyer, and Ausubel, 1996), (Micó and Caselles, 1998), (Micó, Caselles, Soler and Ferrer, 1999), (Micó, Caselles and Soler, 2002). In these works, all rates are only time-dependent. In Caselles, Micó, Soler and Sanz (2008) we presented a model in which all rates depend on a specific welfare variable (HDI). But, in the model presented here, the functions on which the population depends are calculated depending on the HDI, GDI, GEM, HPI2 (four welfare variables), and not depending on time.

We cannot present graphically the functions because there are four independent variables. Therefore, in order to validate them we use the analysis of residues and the parameter R^2 . The used historical information is the corresponding to HDI, GDI, GEM, HPI2, and to the years 1998-2005.

With respect to the *women birth rates* corresponding to the application period (1999-2005), they have been obtained dividing women births and population. To fit the birth rate as a function of the welfare variables, we have also considered a logistic curve.

$$TFBI(hdi, gdi, gem, hpi2) = \alpha_7 + \beta_7 \cdot gem \cdot gdi^2 + \gamma_7 \cdot \text{Cos}(\mu_7 \cdot gem \cdot gdi) \quad (34)$$

The *men birth rates* have been obtained analogously.

$$TMBI(hdi, gdi, gem, hpi2) = \alpha_8 + \beta_8 \cdot gem^2 \cdot gdi + \gamma_8 \cdot \text{Cos}(\mu_8 \cdot gem \cdot gdi) \quad (35)$$

The *women death rates* have been obtained analogously.

$$TFDE(hdi, gdi, gem, hpi2) = \alpha_9 + \beta_9 \cdot hpi2^2 \cdot gdi^2 + \gamma_9 \cdot \text{Cos}(\mu_9 \cdot hdi \cdot hpi2) \quad (36)$$

The *men death rates* have been obtained analogously.

$$TMDE(hdi, gdi, gem, hpi2) = \alpha_{10} + \beta_{10} \cdot hdi^2 + \gamma_{10} \cdot \text{Cos}(\mu_{10} hpi2) \quad (37)$$

We can observe that in birth rate functions the welfare variables involved are GEM and GDI. This is obvious because birth rate depends on the social position of women directly, and the welfare variables that measure such position are GDI and GEM.

On the other hand, in death rate functions the welfare variables are HDI and HPI2, because these variables are directly related with death.

In APPENDIX I we present different tables and graphics that show all parameters and the distribution of all residues.

5. Model validation

In order to validate the presented model, we have written it as a set of finite difference equations. These equations have been

programmed in MATHEMATICA introducing the functions fitted in Section 4. Results have been obtained for the period 1999-2005, and the validation has been performed graphically superposing the results obtained for every year and the historical data.

The validation has been considered successful due to three reasons:

- The superposition of historical and calculated data in the first years is very good.
- We have calculated the determination coefficients (an index useful for global validation between data sets):

$$R^2 = \frac{(\sum_i (x_i - \mu_x)(y_i - \mu_y))^2}{\sum_i (x_i - \mu_x)^2 \sum_i (y_i - \mu_y)^2},$$

where (x_i, y_i) are the data to be compared, and μ_x and μ_y are the respective average values.

- We have verified the randomness of the results by means of the maximum relative error.

To check this information, see Figure 10, 11 and 12 in APPENDIX I.

6. Conclusions

The presented model is a substantial advance with respect to the one presented by Caselles, Micó, Soler and Sanz (2008), due to the fact that we have introduced three new welfare variables considered by the UN (besides HDI) in order to explain the variability of birth rates and death rates. That is because birth rates and death rates depend on the same country welfare variables. The immigration and emigration rates don't only depend on country welfare variables but also on the same in the country of arrival.

UN mentioned five welfare variables and we only use four of them because HPI-1¹⁰ is designed for the set of developing countries.

With respect to validation, we can say that, in spite of accepting the performed validation process from a theoretical point of view, we see graphically that with respect to Male

¹⁰ The human poverty index for developing countries.

Population, the fitting curve separates considerably from the historical data. This fact induces us to think that we have to introduce in the model the distinction by ages in order to improve the adjustment of the death rates and the emigration rates. That introduction will probably improve the adjustment of population curves to historical data because, due to other models (Micó, Caselles, Soler, and Ferrer, 1999), (Micó, Caselles, and Soler, 2002), (Osborn, 1963), we know that the model validations are improved by introducing the distinction per sexes and ages.

Another improvement could be obtained by the conversion of this deterministic model into a stochastic model (Chowdhury and Allen, 2001).

Other advance, if we want that immigration and emigration rates depend on welfare variables, could be to create two models: one for the native land and another one for the arrival land.

Finally, we also are thinking about elaborating a generic model, which could be used for any country, already developed or in developing process, in order to look for solutions for the sustainable growth of the societies in which the generational relief is in danger.

7. References

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APPENDIX I

In this Appendix we include the Forrester's diagram, the tables and diagrams that we have used in order to obtain the approximation of the output variables and the model validation.

In the diagrams, lines indicate approximate information and points indicate the real data obtained from the data bases (I.N.E).

TFEM	α_i	β_i	μ_i	γ_i		TMEM	α_i	β_i	μ_i	γ_i
i=1	1.67928	0.00157988	1996	- 0.000110753		i=3	1.86558	0.0159898	1995	- 0.0021828
i=2	1.80529	0.00455055	2002	1.55771		i=4	1.62506	0.00401888	2002	1.538

Table 3: Parameter values for TFEM(t)

Table 4: Parameter values for TMEM

TFIN	α_i	β_i	μ_i	γ_i		TMIN	α_i	β_i	μ_i	γ_i
i=5	1.08076	0.0116099	1998	7.43862		i=6	0.984533	0.0139951	1998	6.88495

Table 5: Parameter values for TFIN(t)

Table 6: Parameter values for TMIN(t)

TFBI	α_i	β_i	μ_i	γ_i		TMBI	α_i	β_i	μ_i	γ_i
i=7	0.007793	0.002745	16.887851	0.000509		i=8	0.008907	0.002411	16.887851	0.000549

Table 7: Parameter values for TFB(hdi, gdi, gem, hpi2)

Table 8: Parameter values for TMBI(hdi, gdi, gem, hpi2)

TFDE	α_i	β_i	μ_i	γ_i		TMDE	α_i	β_i	μ_i	γ_i
i=9	0.010140	- 0.000016	5.862193	0.000231		i=10	0.014420	-0.005871	2.727273	0.000136

Table 9: Parameter values for TFDE(hdi, gdi, gem, hpi2)

Table 10: Parameter values for TMDE(hdi, gdi, gem, hpi2)

Figure 2: Fitted function (solid line) and real data (dots) for Female Emigration Rate along time in Spain, from the welfare variables in the period 1996-2005. $R^2 = 0.6281$. For Kolmogorov-Smirnov's contrast, the theoretical deviation $D(\alpha, 17) > 0.232379$, for any level of significance $\alpha \geq 0.01$. So, the normality hypothesis is accepted for the residues of the model.

Figure 3: Fitted function (solid line) and real data (dots) for Male Emigration Rate along time in Spain, from the welfare variables in the period 1996-2005. $R^2 = 0.736282$. For Kolmogorov-Smirnov's contrast, the theoretical deviation $D(\alpha, 17) > 0.273736$, for any level of significance $\alpha \geq 0.01$. So, the normality hypothesis is accepted for the residues of the model.

Figure 4: Fitted function (solid line) and real data (dots) for Female Immigration Rate along time in Spain, from the welfare variables in the period 1996-2005. $R^2 = 0.923129$. For Kolmogorov-Smirnov's contrast, the theoretical deviation $D(\alpha, 17) > 0.193791$, for any level of significance $\alpha \geq 0.01$. So, the normality hypothesis is accepted for the residues of the model.

Figure 5: Fitted function (solid line) and real data (dots) for Male Immigration Rate along time in Spain, from the welfare variables in the period 1996-2005. $R^2 = 0.866855$. For Kolmogorov-Smirnov's contrast, the theoretical deviation $D(\alpha, 17) > 0.192803$, for any level of significance $\alpha \geq 0.01$. So, the normality hypothesis is accepted for the residues of the model.

Figure 6: Residues (ordinate) of Female Birth Rate (abscise) in Spain, from the welfare variables in the period 1999-2005. $R^2 = 0.98329$. For Kolmogorov-Smirnov's contrast, the theoretical deviation $D(\alpha, 17) > 0.130162$, for any level of significance $\alpha \geq 0.01$. So, the normality hypothesis is accepted for the residues of the model.

Figure 7: Residues (ordinate) of Male Birth Rate (abscise) in Spain, from the welfare variables in the period 1999-2005. $R^2 = 0.980023$. For Kolmogorov-Smirnov's contrast, the theoretical deviation $D(\alpha, 17) > 0.198774$, for any level of significance $\alpha \geq 0.01$. So, the normality hypothesis is accepted for the residues of the model.

Figure 8: Residues (ordinate) of Female Death Rate (abscise) in Spain, from the welfare variables in the period 1999-2005. $R^2 = 0.777056$. For Kolmogorov-Smirnov's contrast, the theoretical deviation $D(\alpha, 17) > 0.130162$, for any level of significance $\alpha \geq 0.01$. So, the normality hypothesis is accepted for the residues of the model.

Figure 9: Residues (ordinate) of Male Death Rate (abscise) in Spain, from the welfare variables in the period 1999-2005. $R^2 = 0.781668$. For Kolmogorov-Smirnov's contrast, the theoretical deviation $D(\alpha, 17) > 0.150537$, for any level of significance $\alpha \geq 0.01$. So, the normality hypothesis is accepted for the residues of the model.

Figure 10: Forecast function (solid line) given by the model and real data (dots) for Spain's Female Population, in the period 1999-2005, $R^2 = 0.699575$, with 1.58236% of maximum relative error. The model is considered validated, since the error does not overcome 5%.

Figure 11: Forecast function (solid line) given by the model and real data (dots) for Spain's Male Population, in the period 1999-2005, $R^2 = 0.475155$ with 2.83259% of maximum relative error. The model is considered validated, since the error does not overcome 5%.

Figure 12: Forecast function (solid line) given by the model and real data (dots) for Spain's Population, in the period 1999-2005, $R^2 = 0.570755$ with 2.19798% of maximum relative error. The model is considered validated, since the error does not overcome 5%.